

Brian Paul Kaess gets invited to Bible Study by Brian Paul Kaess

It was the 1991-1992 school year and I was a Senior at Northeastern Illinois University in Chicago. Besides my studies, I was spending some time with my friend John Carl Toth at his apartment in East Edgewater, just drinking sugared tea, listening to *Enya*, and shooting the breeze about Philosophy, which I was studying at the time. John was like: 'Philosophy is cool, man!' Sometime later he began attending church with the *Jehovah's Witnesses* at their Roger's Park compound and he went through 'a UBF phase' as one might call it. Eventually, he invited me along and we both went to church together, learning more about their grassroots church activities, like going door-to-door to solicit worshippers, although I never participated in that way.

While at church he introduced me to a cute girl, named Mary, and her seemingly British-born dad, John. They seemed almost inseparable in their church attendance. Then, after a while, John Toth came to me and said: 'John would like you to study the Bible with him and his daughter Mary at their house', which I believe may have been on Hood Ave. in Edgewater. At this time, towards the end of Senior Year, I was swamped with school projects and trying to make sure I graduated on time. I wish this would have happened a year or two later, but at that time, I said 'No.' I was a bit weary of 'time-suckers' and didn't really grasp the opportunity to get to know John and Mary better.

Also, at that time, I didn't really grasp the central tenets of 'Jehovah's' being a sort of C.O. or Conscientious Objector kind of crowd. I mean, I appreciate pacifism, but would never really go that way with the military, since I am more of a classic 'war-church' kind of guy. In any case, I missed an opportunity to study with Mary and John and not give a damn about that darn military. Like my friend John Toth once said: 'It takes some mighty strong pussy to make a man change Gods!' Let us hope, after reading this short epistle, that the reader does not believe that chivalry is an anachronism.